

Total Variation regularized reconstruction for enhancing the quality of few-view industrial computed tomography applied to image analysis

Maryam Bahrkazemi^{1,2}, Alexander Rohde¹, Jonathan Hess¹, Patricio Guerrero², Sven Gondrom-Linke¹, Wim Dewulf²

¹Volume Graphics GmbH, 69115 Heidelberg, Germany, e-mail: maryam.bahrkazemi@hexagon.com, alexander.rohde@hexagon.com, jonathan.hess@hexagon.com, sven.gondrom-linke@hexagon.com,

²KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium, e-mail: maryam.bahrkazemi@kuleuven.be, patricio.guerrero@kuleuven.be, wim.dewulf@kuleuven.be.

Abstract

The few-view image reconstruction problem is one of the challenging research areas in industrial Computed Tomography(CT). On the one hand, acquiring enough data for reconstruction leads to a longer scanning time, which may not be applicable in industrial CT. On the other hand, reconstructing under-sampled data leads to artifacts and inaccurate image analysis. To get a usable reconstruction for image analysis, from the insufficient data caused by quick cone beam CT scans, we use a Total Variation (TV) regularized optimization problem. A split Bregman implementation is used to solve the TV regularized CT reconstruction problem. To evaluate the quality of the few-view reconstruction produced by the split Bregman, we perform gray value analysis and porosity analysis. The comparison is done against the established reconstruction algorithms OSSART and FDK approximate formula, using real and realistically simulated CT data in cone beam geometry.

Keywords: X-Ray Computed Tomography, Cone Beam Geometry, Total Variation Regularization, Split Bregman Algorithm, OSSART Iterative Reconstruction Method, FDK, Gray Value Analysis, Porosity Quantification.

1 Introduction

The application of computed tomography is observing the interior of an object, to which we do not have direct access. The measurements made by the detector for each angle in the cone beam geometry are called view or projection. The resulting CT scan has one view per angle recorded. Multiple factors influence reconstruction quality and the possibilities for further image analysis of the reconstruction. The important factors are: the number of views, resolution, noise level, and reconstruction algorithm [1]. There are two categories of common reconstruction techniques: analytical methods and iterative approaches. The common analytical method for cone beam scanning reconstruction is the FDK approach [2], whereas the other widely used algorithm for CT imaging is the algebraic reconstruction technique [3]. For many applications, analytical methods, such as FDK, perform well where there are plenty of projections to validate the Nyquist criterion. However, scanning time plays an important role in industrial CT, and one solution for taking a shorter scanning time is limiting the number of views. When the projection data are insufficient for the reconstruction of the industrial CT, FDK produces artifacts in the reconstructed image, which affect the image analysis.

Computed tomography reconstruction is an inverse problem. Many different methods have been proposed to solve inverse problems [4]. Among all the developed methods for CT reconstruction, TV regularized optimization has been investigated for few-view CT reconstruction [5]. In this paper, we focus on using the TV regularized optimization problem for few-view cone-beam industrial CT reconstruction. The TV penalty term assists in finding the optimal solution of the inverse problem by utilizing the gradient of the image as a constraint [6]. To find the minimum of the TV-regularized loss function defined for cone beam CT reconstruction, we implemented the split Bregman algorithm as an iterative solver, introduced by Goldstein and Osher [7]. The split Bregman algorithm had been introduced in [7] for general $L1$ regularized optimization problems and applied to image denoising problem and MRI reconstruction. The split Bregman algorithm includes two main minimization steps: the smooth minimization and the non-smooth but element-wise separable step that can be minimized as a proximal operator [9].

Since then, the split Bregman algorithm has been applied to a variety of $L1$ regularization problems, for instance in [10], Yin et al. investigate the application of the split Bregman algorithm in compressed sensing. Also, the efficiency of the split Bregman for image denoising and deblurring-restoration is discussed in [11] and [12], respectively. In both papers, the split Bregman applied to problems with different noise models, like Gaussian, Laplacian, and Poisson, which leads to solving the problem with the specific data fidelity terms for each noise model. Also, the role of the related parameters to the data fidelity term had been investigated. In [14], Chen and Xu studied the Split Bregman algorithm applied to 2D CT reconstruction, while its inner optimization problem is solved by the linearized Bregman method. Finally, the most similar work to our study is [15], which studies the split Bregman algorithm solving TV-regularization problem with a priori knowledge. In fact, it considers the a priori knowledge as a separate regularization term for medical parallel beam CT reconstruction. Moreover, for solving the inner optimization step in the split Bregman algorithm, the steepest descent method is implemented. The initial guess used is an ART reconstruction of the 2D CT scan.

In this paper, we reconstruct a real cone beam CT scan and realistically simulated cone beam CT data with a specific number of

defects using the split Bregman algorithm as a TV regularization solver. The reconstructions are evaluated by performing gray value analysis on the reconstruction of real data and porosity analysis on the reconstruction of simulated data. The next section is dedicated to the algebraic reconstruction model of CT and the TV regularized optimization problem. In section 3, we discuss the idea behind the split Bregman and various steps of the algorithm. The evaluation and analyses of the few-view reconstruction of split Bregman with real and simulated data compared to OSSART and FDK, are presented in section 4.

2 Total Variation Regularization

The inverse problem of computed tomography reconstruction is formulated as

$$Au = f, \quad (1)$$

where A is the cone-beam Radon operator, f refers to the measurements, and u is the desired image. When it comes to reconstructing a limited number of projections, the inverse problem of CT is significantly ill-posed. One way to handle an ill-posed inverse problem is, to use the regularization term. Regularization term assists to converge to a unique and stable minimum solution [1, 4, 6]. According to [10], many problems in imaging can be modeled as $L1$ -regularization. The general form of $L1$ -regularized problem is defined

$$\min_u \|u\|_1 + F(u), \quad (2)$$

where $F(u)$ is a convex and differentiable function called the data fidelity term. Many algorithms have been developed for $L1$ -regularization minimization upon the following iterative approach

$$u^{k+1} \leftarrow \arg \min_u \|u\|_1 + \frac{1}{2\beta} \|u - (u^k - \beta \nabla F(u^k))\|_2^2, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (3)$$

where u^k is the solution of iterative method in k th iteration and β is the step size. Since u is component-wise separable, *shrink* function or *soft thresholding* comes in handy to find the minimum solution.

$$u_i^{k+1} = \text{shrink}((u^k - \beta \nabla F(u^k))_i, \beta), \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (4)$$

Shrink operator of $x, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$ is defined as [7]

$$\text{shrink}(x, \beta) = \frac{x}{|x|} * \max(|x| - \beta, 0). \quad (5)$$

The total variation (TV) regularized problem originally was introduced by Rudin, Osher, and Fatemi for image denoising [16]. The total variation of a function in its interval is the accumulative sum of the change of the function in each monotonic sub-interval. Obviously, the more oscillations a function has, the larger the total variation is. On a monotonic interval, TV is calculated as the absolute difference of the values of the function in its endpoints. Therefore, the absolute sum of the forward finite difference of a discrete function is equal to its total variation. Since in this paper, the discrete gradient is defined as the forward finite difference, the TV semi-norm is the $L1$ norm of the discrete gradient (∇) of the image $\|u\|_{TV} \approx \|\nabla u\|_1$ [11]. The iterative procedure of (3) can be modified to apply to the total variation regularization problem [10]

$$\min_u \|u\|_{TV} + F(u), \quad (6)$$

Consider the data fidelity term $F(u) = \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au - f\|_2^2$ in equation (6); hence, the TV regularized optimization problem of CT reconstruction reformulated as

$$\min_u \|u\|_{TV} + \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au - f\|_2^2, \quad (7)$$

which is equivalent to the constraint problem of

$$\min_u \|u\|_{TV}, \quad \text{subject to } Au = f. \quad (8)$$

It is proved in [14, Lemma 2.1] that the equations (7) and (8) are equivalent. Since the $L1$ term in (7) is neither differentiable nor separable, the smooth optimization approach and simple thresholding operator (5) are not applicable. In order to overcome these difficulties, the Split Bregman algorithm applies the operator splitting concept [9]. The split Bregman algorithm is a non-smooth convex optimization solver, which we describe in detail in the next section.

3 Split Bregman

According to Goldstein and Osher [7], let's consider equation (7), the split Bregman substitutes the non-smooth functional $\|\nabla u\|_1$, which is not separable, with a separable $L1$ term, and makes the problem constraint as the following:

$$\arg \min_{u,d} \|d\|_1 + \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au - f\|_2^2, \quad \text{subject to } d = \nabla u. \quad (9)$$

where A is the forward projection operator in CT problem and ∇ is the gradient operator. In order to solve the equation (9), it is turned into the following unconstrained problem

$$(u^{k+1}, d^{k+1}) = \min_{d,u} \|d^k\|_1 + \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au^k - f\|_2^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|d^k - \nabla u^k\|_2^2, \quad (10)$$

By applying the Bregman iteration [13], the split Bregman method solves the following problems in each iteration:

$$(u^{k+1}, d^{k+1}) = \min_{d,u} \|d\|_1 + \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au - f\|_2^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|d - \nabla u - b^k\|_2^2, \quad (11)$$

$$b^{k+1} = b^k + (\nabla u^{k+1} - d^{k+1}). \quad (12)$$

where b is the Bregman variable in Bregman iteration algorithm and λ is a positive constant. Considering the equation (11), as the $L1$ and $L2$ terms are separated, we are able to minimize the loss function (11) with respect to u and d individually. Therefore, according to [7], two steps are considered:

$$\text{w.r.t. } u : u^{k+1} = \min_u \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au^k - f\|_2^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|d^k - \nabla u^k - b^k\|_2^2, \quad (13)$$

$$\text{w.r.t. } d : d^{k+1} = \min_d \|d^k\|_1 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|d^k - \nabla u^{k+1} - b^k\|_2^2. \quad (14)$$

The optimization problem of (13) is differentiable; hence, the problem is solvable with any smooth optimization technique, such as conjugated gradient, Gauss-Seidel, gradient descent, etc. In this paper, we have applied the gradient descent method as following:

$$u^{k+1} = u^k - \alpha(\mu A^T (Au^k - f) + \lambda \nabla^T (\nabla u^k + b^k - d^k)). \quad (15)$$

In the second step (14), we can compute the optimal value of d using shrink operator (5). Summing up all the above descriptions yield the following split Bregman algorithm 1:

Algorithm 1 Split Bregman Algorithm

Initialize : $b^0 = d^0 = 0$, $u^0 = \text{initial guess}$,

while $\|Au^k - f\|_2^2 > \varepsilon^2$ **do**

$$u^{k+1} = \min_u \left\{ \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au - f\|_2^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|d - \nabla(u) - b^k\|_2^2 \right\}$$

$$d^{k+1} = \text{shrink}(\nabla u^{k+1} + b^k, \frac{1}{\lambda})$$

$$b^{k+1} = b^k + (\nabla u^{k+1} - d^{k+1})$$

end while

4 Numerical Results

In this section, we reconstruct the real and realistically simulated CT data with FDK, OSSART, and split Bregman algorithms. We call the cone beam reconstruction algorithm of split Bregman SB-TV. To assess the results of reconstruction algorithms, we perform gray value analysis for real data and porosity analysis for simulated data. The forward projection, backward projection, FDK, and OSSART are the implementations of the Tigre toolbox in Python [17, 18]. The gray value analysis and porosity quantification are performed by VGSTUDIO MAX 2022.3 software [19]. All iterative reconstructions are performed in 10 iterations without any non-negativity constraint, and the initial guess is the few-view FDK reconstruction. For the evaluation of the result of iterative reconstruction methods, the data fidelity term $\|Au - f\|_2^2$ and the TV-norm $\|u\|_{TV}$ are used. The data fidelity measures the difference between the forward projection of the reconstruction and the original CT scan.

4.1 Cone beam SB-TV Algorithm

As split Bregman algorithm can be implemented on the problems with multiple $L1$ term, it is possible to consider each axis direction (x, y, z) as a $L1$ norm with its separate gradient in the cone beam CT geometry. According to (9), the TV regularized cone beam CT reconstruction problem is defined as

$$\arg \min_{u,d} |d_x| + |d_y| + |d_z| + \frac{\mu}{2} \|Au - f\|_2^2, \quad \text{subject to} \quad d_x = \nabla_x u, d_y = \nabla_y u, d_z = \nabla_z u, \quad (16)$$

Let's assume the size of image is $M \times M \times M$, the gradient operator and the adjoint of gradient operator are defined according to [20] as:

$$\nabla_x u_{i,j,l} = \begin{cases} u_{i+1,j,l} - u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } i < M, \\ 0 & \text{if } i = M, \end{cases}, \quad \nabla_y u_{i,j,l} = \begin{cases} u_{i,j+1,l} - u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } j < M, \\ 0 & \text{if } j = M, \end{cases}, \quad \nabla_z u_{i,j,l} = \begin{cases} u_{i,j,l+1} - u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } l < M, \\ 0 & \text{if } l = M, \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\nabla_x^T u_{i,j,l} = \begin{cases} u_{i-1,j,l} - u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } 1 < i < M, \\ -u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } i = 1, \\ u_{i-1,j,l} & \text{if } i = M, \end{cases}, \quad \nabla_y^T u_{i,j,l} = \begin{cases} u_{i,j-1,l} - u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } 1 < j < M, \\ -u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } j = 1, \\ u_{i,j-1,l} & \text{if } j = M, \end{cases}, \quad \nabla_z^T u_{i,j,l} = \begin{cases} u_{i,j,l+1} - u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } l < M, \\ -u_{i,j,l} & \text{if } l = 1, \\ u_{i,j,l-1} & \text{if } l = M. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

Considering the algorithm 1 and the gradient descent implementation in (15), the implemented SB-TV algorithm for cone beam reconstruction is shown in algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 SB-TV Algorithm

Initialize : $b_x^0 = b_y^0 = b_z^0 = d_x^0 = d_y^0 = d_z^0 = 0, u^0 = \text{few-view FDK}, i = 10,$

while $\|Au^k - f\|_2^2 > \varepsilon^2$ and $k < i$ **do**

$$a = A^T (Au^k - f)$$

$$b = \nabla_x^T (\nabla_x u^k + b_x^k - d_x^k) + \nabla_y^T (\nabla_y u^k + b_y^k - d_y^k) + \nabla_z^T (\nabla_z u^k + b_z^k - d_z^k)$$

$$u^{k+1} = u^k - \alpha(\mu a + \lambda b)$$

$$d_x^{k+1} = \text{shrink}(\nabla_x u^{k+1} + b_x^k, \frac{1}{\lambda})$$

$$d_y^{k+1} = \text{shrink}(\nabla_y u^{k+1} + b_y^k, \frac{1}{\lambda})$$

$$d_z^{k+1} = \text{shrink}(\nabla_z u^{k+1} + b_z^k, \frac{1}{\lambda})$$

$$b_x^{k+1} = b_x^k + (\nabla_x u^{k+1} - d_x^{k+1})$$

$$b_y^{k+1} = b_y^k + (\nabla_y u^{k+1} - d_y^{k+1})$$

$$b_z^{k+1} = b_z^k + (\nabla_z u^{k+1} - d_z^{k+1})$$

end while

4.2 Real data reconstruction

The real data is a 3143 view scan, of 2000×2000 pixels, measured by an industrial Nikon XTH 225 ST CT system at KU Leuven. For ease of computation and reducing the run time of the reconstruction algorithms, the detector size of the real data is reduced to 500×500 by VGSTUDIO Max (Volume Graphics GmbH). To create a data set for few-view reconstruction of real data, the number of views was reduced from 3143 to 105 equally spaced views. The gray value analysis is performed to obtain information on the standard deviation in each reconstruction.

In figure 1, the real data reconstructions by FDK, OSSART, and SB-TV are demonstrated. In the top row, the difference between the better reconstruction of FDK with all the views, and the undesired reconstruction of few-view FDK are visible. There are many limited-view artifacts in the few-view reconstruction of FDK. The bottom row contains the result of the few-view OSSART on the left and the few-view SB-TV on the right. The iterative algorithms with few-view perform better than few-view FDK, as seen in the removal of visible artifacts.

The plots of TV-norm and data fidelity, per iteration, are shown in figure 2. Notice that the initial guess for both iterative methods is the few-view FDK reconstruction, which is displayed as the constant dashed line in both plots. The few-view OSSART and

Figure 3: The 2D and 3D reconstructed volume from real data containing the two ROIs on the left and right, respectively. The ROI inside the object is in blue, and the ROI outside the object is in yellow.

SB-TV reconstruction improved the few-view reconstruction of FDK. According to the data fidelity plot, the iterative methods minimized the data fidelity term in a similar fashion. However, according to the plot of the TV-norm per iteration, the few-view SB-TV algorithm, besides reducing the data fidelity term, tries to converge to a solution with a smaller TV-norm in each iteration which assists in delivering a better reconstruction.

The histogram of the gray values for the mentioned reconstruction algorithms is shown in figure 4. There is a close similarity between the range of gray values in the reconstruction of the few-view SB-TV and full-view FDK reconstruction, while few-view FDK and few-view OSSART have slightly wider ranges. SB-TV is the only few-view Algorithm which is able to replicate the shape of the air and material peeks of the full-view FDK.

Figure 4: The gray values histogram of the real data reconstructions.

Table 1: The gray value analysis of the first region of interest (inside the reconstructed volume).

Reconstruction method	No. of projections	No. of iteration	Mean gray values	Standard deviation
FDK	3143	-	23146.115	340.422
FDK	105	-	23152.490	812.814
OSSART	105	10	23213.689	695.164
SB-TV	105	10	23154.875	271.323

Table 2: The gray value analysis of the first region of interest (outside the reconstructed volume).

Reconstruction method	No. of projections	No. of iteration	Mean gray values	Standard deviation
FDK	3143	-	8346.267	123.520
FDK	105	-	8350.185	628.203
OSSART	105	10	8382.950	511.493
SB-TV	105	10	8346.988	126.899

Figure 3 displays the two regions of interest (ROI) used for gray value analysis. As seen in the 2D and 3D view the blue ROI is completely inside the object and contains only one material. The yellow ROI is outside of the object and contains only air. Table 1 contains the gray value analysis results for all three reconstruction algorithms for the blue ROI inside of the object, and table 2 shows the results for the yellow ROI containing only air.

We use gray value analysis to get an idea of the reconstruction quality compared to the full-view FDK, and the algorithm’s ability to reduce noise during reconstruction. The metrics are the mean gray value and the standard deviation to make the comparison. Each ROI contains only one material; hence, the mean gray value should be close to the accepted as good, full-view FDK reconstruction. A lower standard deviation is considered better, because, for a single material, all values should be close to the mean.

Table 1 shows the values for the blue ROI inside of the object. Regarding the standard deviation, SB-TV performs much better than OSSART and few-view FDK. The few-view SB-TV even beats full-view FDK, because the total variation minimization

removes a lot of noise during reconstruction, unlike the full-view FDK reconstruction. Table 2 contains the results for the yellow air ROI. For the standard deviation, the results of the material ROI are mirrored with SB-TV, having a much lower standard deviation than the few-view FDK and OSSART. In conclusion, the most influential result of the gray value analysis of the two ROIs is a significant reduction of the standard deviation achieved by the total variation minimization of the few-view SB-TV compared to the two established reconstruction algorithms.

4.3 Realistically simulated data reconstruction

The realistically simulated data has been generated using the simulation pipeline provided by Fuchs et al. [21]. The simulation pipeline generated a 1200 projection scan of an aluminum part with a resolution of 500×500 detector pixels with 50 predefined defects added. The simulation pipeline uses aRTist 2. [22] to simulate data realistically. The number of views for the few-view reconstruction is 60 views. We run VGEasyPore algorithm with default parameters, to perform porosity analysis of the simulated data reconstruction. Additionally, since the simulation pipeline provides the ground truth, we evaluate the voxel-based Intersection over Union (IoU) to determine the overall quality of the reconstruction [21].

$$IoU = \frac{\text{reconstruction} \cap \text{ground truth}}{\text{reconstruction} \cup \text{ground truth}} \quad (19)$$

The IoU is a value between 0 and 1. The closer the IoU is to 1, the more voxels are correctly identified as part of a defect.

Figure 5: The simulated data reconstruction in three different axis intersections.

The reconstruction of simulated data is manifested in figure 5. In the top row, on the right side, the reconstruction of the few-view FDK is heavily corrupted by artifacts, while the FDK of full projections has successfully reconstructed the data. In the bottom row, the few-view reconstructions of iterative methods in 10 iterations are placed. The data fidelity term for the few-view OSSART (on the left) is equal to 13,616, while the under-sampled reconstruction of SB-TV (on the right) has a data fidelity of 5994. Hence, the smaller data fidelity demonstrates better reconstruction of the few-view SB-TV.

Table 3: Porosity analysis of simulated data reconstruction with 50 determined defects. The VGEasyPore algorithm is applied for porosity quantification, and the evaluation metric is Intersection over Union.

Reconstruction method	No. of projections	No. of iteration	IoU	No. of detected pores
FDK	1200	-	0.7789	49
FDK	60	-	0.350	0
OSSART	60	10	0.3839	14
SB-TV	60	10	0.5558	27

The table 3 contains the information on porosity analysis of the three different reconstruction methods shown in figure 5. According to the table, the FDK reconstruction with enough projections has the biggest IoU of 0.7789, and the VGEasyPore algorithm detected 49 pores out of 50 in its reconstruction. The Few-view FDK reconstruction has the smallest IoU with 0.350, and the VGEasyPore algorithm was not able to detect any pore in its reconstruction due to severe artifacts. The VGEasyPore algorithm detected only 14 pores in the few-view reconstruction of OSSART, and its IoU is 0.3539. However, the few-view SB-TV reconstruction delivered better results than the other two reconstruction methods since the VGEasyPore algorithm found 27 defects,

Figure 6: The detection of pores in three different reconstructions.

and its IoU is 0.5558.

Figure 6 shows the detection of pores in full-view FDK (on the left), few-view FDK (in the middle), and the few-view SB-TV (on the right). According to the figure 6 and the table 3, the VGEasyPore algorithm was not able to find any pore in the few-view FDK reconstruction because of artifacts and low quality of the reconstruction. Also, the pores in the few-view OSSART reconstruction were detected completely falsely due to corruption of reconstruction by artifact. However, the VGEasyPore algorithm has been able to detect the big pores in the few-view SB-TV reconstruction similarly detected in full-view FDK, but the SB-TV algorithm removed the small pores during the reconstruction as part of the total variation minimization.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we compared the results of the gray value and porosity analyses of three different reconstruction methods: split Bregman (SB-TV), OSSART, and FDK applied to real and simulated data in the few-view industrial CT. For incomplete measurements i.e. few-view, iterative reconstruction techniques are always better than the FDK approximate formula, because they try to find the missing values by solving the inverse problem. According to the analysis of our numerical result, the split Bregman as a TV regularized optimization-based reconstruction performs very promising and deserves further investigation for the reconstruction of under-sampled CT data.

TV regularized reconstruction performs better because when the problem is ill-posed and there are many solutions for minimization, TV norms take on the additional role of choosing the image with the sparsest gradient [23]. As shown in figure 2, the split Bregman algorithm converges to the minimum solution with a smaller total variation in each iteration. This characteristic of the algorithm reduces noise and converges to a better reconstruction, but, as shown in figure 6, aggressive total variation minimization can introduce errors in the reconstruction by, for example, removing voids that exist in the scanned object. However, SB-TV shows promise, detecting most of the pores in the correct position in 10 iterations, while the few-view reconstructions of FDK and OSSART do not yield a result usable for image analysis.

The minimization of total variation seems to help with further image analyses, but how good total variation is as an indicator of reconstruction quality should be analyzed further. A problem with the current SB-TV setup is the strong dependence on accurate parameters to perform well, further research into automatic parameter calculation would be needed to use SB-TV without requiring manual parameter search. Because 10 iterations take a considerable amount of time to compute, in the future we want to reduce the number of iterations needed by the SB-TV algorithm using a priori information.

Acknowledgements

This research was co-financed by the European Union H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020 under grant agreement no. 956172 (xCTing). The authors would like to thank all their colleagues at Volume Graphics GmbH, especially Patrick Fuchs in Research & Development and Markus Woyde in Technical Consulting. Also, our thanks go to Simon Bellens, who provided the real CT data for this study.

References

- [1] J. S. Jørgensen, Sparse image reconstruction in computed tomography, 2013.
- [2] L. A. Feldkamp, L. c. Davis, J. W. Kress, Practical cone-beam algorithm, *Josa a1*, no. 6 (1984): 612-619.
- [3] F. Natterer, The mathematics of computerized tomography. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 2001.
- [4] M. Benning, M. Burger, Modern regularization methods for inverse problems, *Acta Numerica* 27 (2018): 1-111.
- [5] E.Y. Sidky, C. Kao, X. Pan, Accurate image reconstruction from few-views and limited-angle data in divergent-beam CT, *Journal of X-ray Science and Technology* 14, no. 2 (2006): 119-139.

- [6] A. Chambolle, V. Caselles, D. Cremers, M. Novaga, T. Pock, An introduction to total variation for image analysis. Theoretical foundations and numerical methods for sparse recovery, 2010 Jul 30; 9(263-340): 227.
- [7] T. Goldstein, S. Osher, the split Bregman method for L1-regularized problems, SIAM journal on imaging sciences 2, no. 2 (2009): 323-343.
- [8] R. Glowinski, S. J. Osher, W. Yin, eds, Splitting methods in communication, imaging, science, and engineering. Springer, 2017.
- [9] N. Parikh, S. Boyd, Proximal algorithms, Foundations and trends® in Optimization 1, no. 3 (2014): 127-239.
- [10] W. Yin, S. Osher, D. Goldfarb, J. Darbon, Bregman iterative algorithms for l1-minimization with applications to compressed sensing, SIAM Journal on Imaging Sciences, 1, 143–168. LIST OF FIGURES (2008).
- [11] G. Pascal, Rudin-Osher-Fatemi total variation denoising using split Bregman, Image Processing On Line 2 (2012): 74-95.
- [12] P. Getreuer, Total variation deconvolution using split Bregman, Image Processing On Line 2 (2012): 158-174.
- [13] L.M. Bregman, The relaxation method of finding the common point of convex sets and its application to the solution of problems in convex programming, USSR computational mathematics and mathematical physics 7, no. 3 (1967): 200-217.
- [14] C. Chen, G. Xu, A new linearized split Bregman iterative algorithm for image reconstruction in sparse-view X-ray computed tomography, Computers Mathematics with Applications 71, no. 8 (2016): 1537-1559.
- [15] L. Deng, P. Feng, M. Chen, P. He, B. Wei, An improved total variation minimization method using prior images and split-Bregman method in CT reconstruction, BioMed Research International 2016 (2016).
- [16] L. Rudin, S. Osher, and E. Fatemi, Nonlinear total variation based noise removal algorithms, Physica D: nonlinear phenomena 60, no. 1-4 (1992): 259-268.
- [17] A. Biguri, M. Dosanjh, S. Hancock, M. Soleimani, TIGRE: a MATLAB-GPU toolbox for CBCT image reconstruction, Biomedical Physics Engineering Express 2, no. 5 (2016): 055010.
- [18] A. Biguri, R. Lindroos, R. Bryll, H. Towsyfyhan, H. Deyhle, I. El khalil Harrane, R. Boardman, M. Mavrogordato, M. Dosanjh, S. Hancock, T. Blumensath, Arbitrarily large tomography with iterative algorithms on multiple GPUs using the TIGRE toolbox, Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing 146 (2020): 52-63.
- [19] Volume Graphics GmbH, VGSTUDIO MAX 2022.3, <https://www.volumegraphics.com/>, 2022 (accessed 19 December 2022).
- [20] A. Chambolle, An algorithm for total variation minimization and applications, Journal of Mathematical imaging and vision 20, no. 1 (2004): 89-97.
- [21] P. Fuchs, T. Kroeger, C. S. Garbe, Defect detection in CT scans of cast aluminum parts: a machine vision perspective, Neurocomputing 453 (2021): 85-96.
- [22] C. Bellon, A. Deresch, C. Gollwitzer, G.-R. Jaenisch, Radiographic simulator aRTist: version 2, In 18th World Conference on nondestructive testing, pp. 16-20. 2012.
- [23] E.Y. Sidky, P. Xiaochuan, Image reconstruction in circular cone-beam computed tomography by constrained, total-variation minimization, Physics in Medicine Biology 53, no. 17 (2008): 4777.